

Assessment of the Application of Inquiry Based-Learning Approach on Students' Motivation and Academic Performance on Teaching History in Tertiary Institutions, Jigawa State

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Abstract

The study was conducted in the year 2024, from November 13, to December 19, during the first semester, using a quasi-experimental design. A judgmental sampling technique was employed to select 22 history students from Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel, who were then assigned to treatment and control groups. The treatment group was taught using the Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) approach, while the control group received instruction through the lecture-based approach. To monitor lecturers, the Inquiry-Based Learning Rating Scale (IBLRS) was used. Students' performance and motivation were assessed using the Students' Assessment Test (SAT) and a questionnaire. The results of the study revealed that the Inquiry-Based Learning approach is more effective than the lecture-based approach in enhancing students' performance. Additionally, the study found that IBL improves students' motivation in history education. However, a gender disparity in motivation levels was observed following the implementation of IBL in history teaching. Based on these findings, the study recommends that lecturers incorporate the Inquiry-Based Learning approach in teaching history at tertiary institutions.

Keywords: Inquiry-Based Learning, Student Motivation, Academic Performance, Tertiary Institutions, Jigawa State.

Introduction

Inquiry-based learning is a student-centered approach that fosters critical thinking, creativity, and active engagement (Sam, 2024). This teaching strategy encourages learners to seek information or knowledge about specific phenomena with minimal guidance from their teacher (Mwenda & Ndayambaje, 2021). It involves students actively engaging in the process of acquiring planned knowledge or information through various methods, such as asking questions, formulating hypotheses, making observations, collecting data, recording findings, interpreting results, and effectively communicating their conclusions (Mwenda & Ndayambaje, 2021). By encouraging exploration, questioning, and independent knowledge construction, inquiry-based learning enables students to develop a deeper understanding of concepts (Sam, 2024).

In history education, inquiry-based learning focuses on developing and evaluating interpretations of the past. Students engage in inquiry tasks that involve investigating authentic historical questions, analyzing multiple sources-including historical documents, artifacts, and historians' accounts-and synthesizing information to form well-supported conclusions (Van Boxtel et al., 2021).

The inquiry-based learning approach allows students to interact with their surroundings, helping them visualize abstract concepts in a concrete manner. This enhances knowledge retention and ultimately improves academic performance (Issaka, 2020). Additionally, inquiry-based learning has been shown to boost students' motivation and academic achievement (Sam, 2024). According to Hagglund (2022), a successful inquiry-based learning approach incorporates key elements such as a driving question, authentic and contextualized inquiry, learner ownership of the problem, teacher support rather than direct instruction, and artifact creation.

In higher education, students are positioned as adult learners who are capable of organizing themselves, collaborating with peers, and independently seeking knowledge to address the challenges they encounter. They integrate new knowledge with prior learning by utilizing their environment and available technologies to enhance their understanding (Syarifuddin, 2023).

Methodology

The study was conducted during the first semester of the 2024 academic year, from November 13th to December 19th. A quasi-experimental design was employed. The population comprised all tertiary institution students in Jigawa State studying history. Using a purposive sampling technique, twenty two (22) students from Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel, were selected and assigned to treatment and control group. The treatment group received instruction through the Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) approach, while the control group was taught using the traditional lecture-based approach. To assess the effectiveness of the teaching approaches (methods), a structured Inquiry-Based Learning Rating Scale (IBLRS) was used to evaluate lecturers. Additionally, a Students' Assessment Test (SAT) and a questionnaire were administered to measure students' performance and motivation.

Results

Table 1: Demographic information of the participants

Variable	Frequency	%
Age-range		
18 - 19 year	8	36.36%
20 - 21 years	10	45.45%
23 – 24 years	4	18.18%
Gender		
Male	16	72.72%
Female	6	27.27%

The table shows that the majority of students (45.5%) were between the ages of twenty (20) and twenty-one (21), followed by those aged 18 to 19 (36.36%), while the smallest group fell within the 23 to 24 age range (18.2%). Additionally, most of the students were male (72.7%).

Table 2: Differences of Students Performance between the Teaching Approach

Method	M±SD	Min.	Max.	df	t-value	prob.
IBLA (n =11)	23.81±10.14	16.0	40	20	6.78	.033
LBLA (n =11)	13.45 ±9.17	04.0	28			
N	22	18.13 ± 11.31				

The results indicate that the teaching approach has a significant impact on students' performance ($t [20] = 6.78, p > 0.05$). The mean score of students taught using the inquiry-based learning approach is higher than that of those taught using the lecture-based approach. This suggests that the inquiry-based learning approach is more effective in enhancing students' performance, as evidenced by the assessment test conducted in this study.

Table 3: Impact of Inquiry Based-Learning Approach on Students' Motivation in Teaching History

N= 11	Agreed	%	Not-Agreed	%
I like Inquiry Based-Learning Approach as students work as a team.	11	100	0	0
The method is very interesting	10	90.9	1	9.0
I feel more satisfaction doing task with others during Inquiry Based-Learning Approach.	6	54.5	5	45.5
I give more attention while doing task during Inquiry Based-Learning Approach.	7	63.6	4	36.4
I spend more time to learn from colleagues during Inquiry Based-Learning Approach.	10	90.9	1	9.0
I don't want to be late if Inquiry Based-Learning Approach is going to be apply in my class	8	72.7	3	27.3
I am very happy during Inquiry Based-Learning Approach	10	90.9	1	9.0

The table shows that 100% of the students expressed a preference for the Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) approach, as it encourages teamwork. Additionally, 90.9% of the students found the method highly engaging. Furthermore, 54.5% reported feeling more satisfied when completing tasks collaboratively during inquiry-based learning. Similarly, 63.6% stated that they paid greater attention while working on tasks using this approach. Moreover, 90.9% of the students indicated that they spent more time learning from their peers during inquiry-based learning. Additionally, 72.7% agreed that they did not want to be late when the inquiry-based learning approach was implemented in their class. Another 90.9% of students reported feeling very happy during inquiry-based learning activities. Overall, the table demonstrates that the percentage of students who agreed with the positive statements about inquiry-based learning is consistently higher than those who disagreed. This suggests that the inquiry-based learning approach effectively enhances students' motivation in history education.

Table 4: Gender difference in Inquiry Based-Learning Approach on Students' Motivation in Teaching History

	Male(n=8)				Female(n=3)			
	AGR	%	NTA	%	AGR	%	NTA	%
I like Inquiry Based-Learning Approach as students work as a team.	8	100%	0	0%	3	100%	0	0%
The method is very interesting	7	87.5%	1	12.5%	3	100%	0	0%
I feel more satisfaction doing task with others during Inquiry Based-Learning Approach.	6	75.0%	2		1	33.3%	2	66.7%
I give more attention while doing task during Inquiry Based-Learning Approach.	4	50.0%	4	50.0%	3	100%	0	0%
I spend more time to learn from colleagues during Inquiry Based-Learning Approach.	6	75.0%	2	25.0%	3	100%	0	0%
I don't want to be late if Inquiry Based-Learning Approach is going to be apply in my class	6	75.0%	2	25.0%	2	66.7%	1	33.3%
I am very happy during Inquiry Based-Learning Approach	6	75.0%	2	25.0%	3	100%	0	0%

The table shows that both male and female students equally favored the Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) approach, with 100% expressing a preference for it due to its emphasis on teamwork. This indicates no gender disparity in students' overall preference for the method. However, differences emerged in specific aspects of motivation. A higher percentage of

female students (100%) found the approach very interesting compared to male students (87.5%). Conversely, more male students (75.0%) reported feeling satisfied when completing tasks with others during inquiry-based learning compared to female students (33.3%). Female students were more attentive during tasks, with 100% stating they paid greater attention, compared to 50% of male students. Similarly, all female students (100%) reported spending more time learning from their peers, while 75.0% of male students said the same. On the other hand, a greater percentage of male students (75.0%) stated they did not want to be late when inquiry-based learning was implemented in their class, compared to 66.7% of female students. Additionally, all female students (100%) reported feeling very happy during IBL, compared to 75.0% of male students. Overall, the table highlights a gender disparity in motivation following the implementation of the inquiry-based learning approach in history teaching.

Discussions

The findings of this study reveal that the Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) approach enhances students' performance more effectively than the conventional lecture-based approach. This aligns with the findings of Sam (2024), who reported that inquiry-based learning positively impacts students' academic performance. Similarly, this study supports the research of Hagglund (2022), who documented higher scores among students taught using inquiry-based learning compared to those in a control group taught under a traditional teacher-centered approach. Hagglund emphasized that implementing inquiry-based learning in history classrooms significantly improves students' performance.

Further reinforcing these findings, Syarifuddin (2023) reported that students in an inquiry-based learning setting demonstrated a higher mastery of concepts than those in conventional learning environments. Additionally, the results of this study are consistent with the research of Kaçar et al. (2021), who found that inquiry-based learning enhances academic performance not only in science classes but also in subjects such as arts, foreign languages, and social studies. Given the similarities between social studies and history in terms of content, this suggests that inquiry-based learning is particularly effective in history education. Kaçar et al. (2021) concluded that inquiry-based learning yields more effective results at the high school level.

The findings of this study are also supported by Pesqueira (2020), who described inquiry-based learning as an effective and engaging instructional method that enhances student learning. Similarly, Voet and De Wever (2016) emphasized that, for students to develop a deep understanding of history, lessons should strike a balance between acquiring historical knowledge and actively engaging in historical inquiry. These findings collectively support the conclusions drawn in this study.

Likewise, the study revealed that inquiry-based learning enhances students' motivation in history education. This finding is consistent with Sam (2024), who documented that inquiry-based learning positively influences students' motivation. It is also in agreement with the study by Byker et al. (2017), which demonstrated that inquiry-based learning can significantly improve students' motivation. Similarly, these findings align with earlier research by Bayram et al. (2013) and Neuby (2010). Bayram et al. (2013) found that inquiry-based activities promote student motivation, while Neuby (2010) argued that effective inquiry facilitation, coupled with ample feedback, plays a crucial role in keeping students engaged in their learning. Furthermore, Neuby (2010) highlighted that two small college studies showed

that in an inquiry-based seminar-style class, students participated more actively, engaged in longer discussions, and interacted with their peers more frequently than in traditional lecture-based courses. Overall, the findings of this study contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the effectiveness of the inquiry-based learning approach in improving both student performance and motivation in teaching history. Additionally, the findings of this study revealed a gender disparity in motivation following the implementation of the inquiry-based learning approach in teaching History. This aligns with the results reported by Li, King, and Wang (2023), who found that boys and girls exhibited distinct motivational patterns in inquiry-based learning contexts.

Conclusion

The inquiry-based learning approach enhances students' performance more effectively than the lecture-based approach. Additionally, it boosts students' motivation in history education. However, a gender disparity exists in motivation levels following the implementation of inquiry-based learning in history teaching.

Recommendations

Based on the outcomes of this study, the following were recommended:

- The study recommends that lecturers integrate the inquiry-based learning approach into their history teaching in tertiary institutions.
- There is a need for professional development programs that focus on designing and implementing inquiry-based lessons tailored to meet the diverse needs of students.

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